

Integrating eDNA and acoustic-trawl data to provide small pelagic biomass estimates for fish stock assessment

Cristina Claver^{1,*}, Beatriz Sobradillo¹, Iñaki Mendibil¹, Oriol Canals¹, Guillermo Boyra¹,
Leire Ibaibarriaga¹, Ryan P. Kelly², Naiara Rodríguez-Ezpeleta¹

¹AZTI, Marine Research, Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), Sukarrieta, Bizkaia 48395, Spain

²University of Washington, School of Marine and Environmental Affairs, Seattle, Washington, 98105, United States

*Corresponding author. AZTI, Marine Research, Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), Txatxarramendi s/n, Sukarrieta, 48395, Bizkaia, Spain.

E-mail: cclaver@azti.es

Abstract

Accurate abundance estimates of fisheries resources are essential for sustainable fisheries management. In response to the growing need for developing more accurate and cost-effective biomass estimation methods, the analysis of environmental DNA (eDNA) has recently emerged as an alternative for fish abundance quantification. However, practical approaches for integrating eDNA data into fisheries assessment remain limited. Here, we introduce a Bayesian joint model that combines acoustic-trawl and eDNA data to estimate fish biomass. Utilizing 209 water eDNA samples and 196 acoustic transects, the model was applied to estimate the distribution and abundance of the European anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*) in the Bay of Biscay. The joint model produced similar estimates to those derived from acoustic observations alone and consistent with known spatial patterns of anchovy, with eDNA data suggesting a broader distribution and potentially higher abundance. This research demonstrates the value of incorporating eDNA data as a complement to acoustic-trawl for stock assessment and illustrates the versatility of joint Bayesian models and their potential application to various species and datasets. Ultimately, our work opens new avenues for more holistic fisheries assessment, underscoring the growing role of eDNA in that context.

Keywords Environmental DNA, acoustic-trawl, biomass, Bayesian joint model, Bay of Biscay anchovy

Introduction

Pelagic fish play key ecological roles in marine ecosystems, acting as trophic intermediaries that regulate plankton populations as well as sustaining biodiversity by serving as prey for a wide range of predators (Iglesias et al. 2025). Their high abundance contributes to nutrient cycling and influences local productivity (Saba et al. 2021). At the same time, they constitute an important global food resource (Fréon et al. 2005), sustaining worldwide economically important fisheries (FAO 2024). Determining “how much fish there is” serves to sustainably manage these marine resources, safeguarding the long-term availability and proper ecosystem functioning. Abundance estimates are central to fisheries assessment, in particular for small pelagics (e.g. anchovies, sardines, herrings), which are characterized by largely fluctuating biomasses and highly dependent on environmental features (Checkley Jr et al. 2017). This makes them particularly vulnerable to overfishing and prone to collapse (Borja et al. 2019).

In last decades, trawl-acoustic methodology has become widespread to estimate abundance and spatial distribution of small pelagic fish globally (Barange et al. 2009) and follows standardized protocols established by international agreements (Demer et al. 2015, Doray et al. (2021)). The method relies on the emission of sound pulses from a transducer, and the subsequent re-

ception and analysis of echoes reflected by organisms in the environment. The intensity of these echoes is related to the density of individuals, enabling the generation of real-time, three-dimensional spatial distribution maps and quantitative biomass estimates (Simmonds and MacLennan 2008), with pelagic trawls providing data on species composition. Importantly, information about age and size of individuals can only be obtained through the catches derived from the trawling operations. Overall, the method has proven to be effective to cover large-scale areas (Fleischer 2005, Stenevik et al. 2015), but, at the same time, trawling has the disadvantages of being invasive, time consuming and dependant on catchability.

In recent years, the analysis of genetic material collected from marine water samples (environmental DNA or eDNA) has demonstrated to be suitable for assessing diversity, distribution and abundance of fish. This approach requires sampling a few litres of water, which makes it a low effort, non-invasive and cost-effective option. Beyond the benefits of easy sampling, eDNA has provided results consistent with those obtained from other established methods and it has outperformed them in some cases. For example, the analysis of eDNA collected from water samples through metabarcoding (i.e. the simultaneous taxonomic assignment of the DNA sequences obtained) results in species composition data that correlates with that obtained from catches, while detecting,

Received: 19 June 2025. Revised: 19 January 2026. Accepted: 20 January 2026

© The Author(s) 2026. Published by Oxford University Press on behalf of International Council for the Exploration of the Sea. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

in general, many more species (Thomsen et al. 2016, Stoeckle et al. 2021, Maiello et al. 2022, Veron et al. 2023). Also, relative abundances obtained through this approach have shown some correlation with those derived from catches (Fraija-Fernández et al. 2020, Zhou et al. 2022), although species-specific deviations and methodological biases were reported, limiting the direct interpretation of eDNA read counts as abundance estimates. Recent research is beginning to clarify sources of these biases (Shaffer et al. 2025), and methodological improvements have been proposed to address them (Shelton et al. 2023). Consequently, eDNA metabarcoding has been promoted as a promising solution to improve fisheries research by increasing detectability while reducing invasiveness and costs (Lacoursière-Roussel et al. 2016).

Beyond qualitative detections and proportional data provided by eDNA metabarcoding, there is a growing interest for the quantification of fish abundance through their eDNA (Gilbey et al. 2021) because the amount of eDNA has shown to consistently correlate with the number of fish and their biomass under controlled conditions (Takahara et al. 2012, Klymus et al. 2015, Eichmiller et al. 2016, Karlsson et al. 2022, Zhang et al. 2024). These studies rely on single-species detection assays that amplify DNA of the target species using quantitative PCR (qPCR) or digital PCR analysis, which are more sensitive than metabarcoding and provide absolute rather than relative eDNA abundance data, which is more directly comparable with biomass. One notable and pioneering study is that of Shelton et al. (2022), which developed a biomass index modelling estimates of hake abundance based on eDNA concentration in a large oceanic area that were equivalent to acoustic estimates, illustrating that both approaches infer fish abundance indirectly (eDNA analysis through fish DNA concentration and acoustics through backscatter intensity) while demonstrating the capacity of eDNA to inform marine fishery assessment as efficiently as well-established data.

Fundamentally, all available methods are approximations that rely of different assumptions and capture different dimensions of abundance. For now, most of the studies attempting to integrate eDNA abundance data in a fisheries assessment context are limited to comparing abundances derived from eDNA data with those obtained from other methods (Knudsen et al. 2019, Salter et al. 2019, Maes et al. 2024), and therefore little effort is focused to assess how to effectively integrate eDNA derived abundance estimates into the assessment. However, rather than competing, these approaches can provide complementary information. Acoustic signals and eDNA concentrations provide independent, positively correlated information about biomass: the more fish present, the stronger the acoustic backscatter and the greater the amount of DNA in the water. Thus, this information could be combined to estimate biomass using multiple lines of evidence, in a more realistic and informed way.

In this regard, recent work has shown that eDNA-based and traditional-based abundance data provide more comprehensive estimations when they are used together and some studies are now opting for combining rather than comparing methods (Guri et al. 2024, Chevrin et al. 2025). Nonetheless, the quantitative combination of eDNA and acoustic-trawl data to estimate fish abundance has not been explored yet and it might be key to incorporate eDNA data into assessment of small pelagics.

In the North East Atlantic Ocean, the Bay of Biscay (BoB) is a temperate gulf where some of the most productive European small pelagic fisheries occur, including the anchovy (*Engraulis en-*

crascolus) (ICES 2022), which underwent a closure (2005–2009) due to a stock collapse. Monitoring programs for this stock include trawl-acoustic methods due to their demonstrated effectiveness for pelagic species (Barange et al. 2009; Simmonds and MacLennan, 2008). Since 2003 acoustic surveys taking place in early autumn (JUVENA) are carried out yearly with the aim of monitoring the juveniles using trawl-acoustic methods (Boyra et al. 2008). After recovery, the anchovy fishery regulation in this area is based on Total Allowable Catch (TAC) established according to an international management plan agreed by different stakeholders (Sánchez et al. 2019, Uriarte et al. 2023). Being such an important and fragile resource, it is of special interest to explore new tools that could improve current monitoring methodologies. Here, we have used both acoustic-trawl and eDNA-derived information collected during the JUVENA surveys to develop a joint Bayesian statistical model to obtain spatial biomass estimates of European anchovy in the BoB, demonstrating the capacity of eDNA to provide valuable, additional information when combined with acoustic data.

Materials and methods

Acoustic-trawl sampling and data processing

Data analysed in this study was collected in the BoB over a period of 6 years (2018 to 2023) during the JUVENA acoustic surveys. This oceanographic campaign has taken place every year since 2003 in early autumn with the aim of estimating the abundance and spatial distribution of anchovy juveniles to quantify the annual recruitment (Boyra et al. 2013).

Details about the acoustic-trawl data processing methodology are explained in Boyra et al. (2023) and in Doray et al. (2021). Briefly, the strategy followed parallel transects perpendicular to the coast with continuous acoustic data recorded to a maximum depth of 500 meters, being the data processed by echointegration per cells of 0.1 nautical miles (NM) long and 5 m height (Fig. 1; Figure S1). Fishing hauls were conducted to validate species composition and to obtain length distribution. The acoustic echointegrations were allocated to species according to catch composition of the trawls and summed over the entire water column, resulting in acoustic abundance values referred to as NASC (Nautical Area Scattering Coefficient; m^2NM^{-2}) (Fig. 2a).

eDNA sample collection and extraction

In parallel to acoustic sampling, water samples were collected during the 2018–2023 JUVENA surveys, resulting in a total of 255 seawater samples distributed among 70 stations (Fig. 1; Figure S1; Table S1). 4–5 litre water samples were collected at each station using a CTD rosette with Niskin bottles and filtered through 0.45 μM Sterivex enclosed filters (Milipore), which are encapsulated, and they minimize the risk of cross-contamination during eDNA sampling. Filters were stored onboard at $-20^\circ C$. DNA was extracted from the filters using DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (Qiagen, USA), following the modifications described in Spens et al. (2017). The concentration of the total extracted DNA ($\mu g/ml$) was calculated with fluorimetry (Qubit™), its quality through UV spectrometry (NanoDrop™) and its integrity through agarose gel electrophore-

Figure 1 Area of study. **(a)** Location of the Bay of Biscay in the Northeast Atlantic Ocean. **(b)** Acoustic transects (green) and eDNA sampling stations (orange) covered in the JUVENA scientific surveys during the 6-year period covered in this work.

sis. Original eDNA samples were diluted to a concentration of 5 ng μl^{-1} for subsequent analyses.

Digital PCR (dPCR) analysis

Water samples were amplified using a QIAcuity Digital PCR system (Qiagen), with a species-specific quantitative method to estimate absolute concentrations of target DNA in seawater. Digital PCR (dPCR) was chosen over standard qPCR due to its superior performance in quantifying low-concentration DNA targets typical of environmental samples, and because it enables absolute quantification without requiring calibration curves (Doi *et al.* 2015, Wood *et al.* 2019). For the detection of European anchovy we used the assays developed by Albaina *et al.* (2015). Because the assay was originally designed for qPCR, we optimized the assay to be run in dPCR and the species-specific fluorescent TaqMan probe

was labelled with FAM. Each reaction consisted of 2 μl of template DNA, 10 μl PCR Master Mix, 3.2 μl of each target-specific probe and primers (5 μM) and 18.4 μl water, resulting in a total reaction volume of 40 μl . Reaction mixes were transferred into the QIAcuity 24-well Nanoplates (maximum 26 000 partitions per reaction). Each plate included a positive control (DNA extracted from anchovy tissue sample) and one negative control (no template). The assay was amplified in the QIAcuity following these conditions: an initial step at 95°C for 2 minutes, followed by 40 cycles alternating between 95°C for 15 seconds and 60°C for 60 seconds. Fluorescence was measured and the number of eDNA copies per reaction volume were calculated by the QIAcuity Software Suite software (version 2.1.7.). The results were visualized using scatterplots created by the software and the positive threshold was manually determined based on the highest droplets in the negative controls of each plate. The software calculates the average number of molecules

Figure 2 Anchovy detections in the BoB during the 6-year-period. **(a)** Depth-integrated acoustic-trawl derived signal (NASC) assigned to anchovy per cell. **(b)** Acoustic signal grided by area. **(c)** Distribution and abundance of anchovy eDNA per sample and grided area showing to which grid each group of samples corresponds. Black diamonds represent samples where no anchovy eDNA was detected.

per partition using Poisson statistics and then transforms this information into concentration (C_r) in the reaction by dividing by partition volume as follows:

$$C_r = -\ln\left(\frac{P_v - P_p}{P_v}\right) \times \left(\frac{P_v}{V_r}\right), \quad (1.1)$$

where P_v corresponds to valid partitions, P_p refers to positive partitions and V_r is the reaction volume (i.e. 40 μ l). The total effective concentration (C_L) (i.e. target eDNA copies per litre of sea water)

was calculated for each sample using the formula:

$$C_L = \frac{C_r \times V_e \times Df_t}{V_w}, \quad (1.2)$$

where C_r is copies of target eDNA per microlitre, V_e is the total elution volume after extraction (in ml), V_w is the volume of filtered sea water (in litres) and Df_t is the unitless dilution factor, calculated as:

$$Df_t = \frac{V_{d1} \times V_{d2}}{V_{a1} \times V_{a2}}, \quad (1.3)$$

where V_{d1} is the volume of the first dilution (i.e. the aliquot), V_{a1} is the volume of the elution used to create the aliquot, V_{d2} is the volume of the second dilution (dPCR reaction) and V_{a2} is the volume of the aliquot used in the dPCR reaction. The final concentration values were calculated as copies of target DNA per litres of seawater.

Spatial gridding of both datasets and acoustic-trawl data resizing

To obtain combinable datasets, we gridded the sampling area horizontally in $\sim 100 \times 150$ nautical miles (NM) length resolution cells (i.e. 0.8×1.2 degrees of latitude and longitude, respectively) and we determined the trawl-acoustic and eDNA data that corresponded to each spatial unit by identifying the samples found in each cell according to their geographic coordinates. Trawl-acoustic data were segmented according to cells and the mean of all depth-integrated values located in each cell was calculated per year. Acoustic sampling effort covered the study area completely, resulting in 120 gridded cell values (Figure S2a). The eDNA samples were not spatially merged and this information was used as point data. A total of 29 cells had eDNA data, with from 3 to 12 point values (average = 10) over the 6-year period (Figure S2b).

Description and application of the spatial joint model

We developed a Bayesian model to integrate both acoustic-trawl and eDNA data to jointly estimate the underlying fish biomass as a latent parameter. We assumed that both acoustic and eDNA data provide imperfect independent information about the underlying true abundance of fish, and that each data type observation is linearly and positively correlated with fish biomass (i.e. the bigger the true fish abundance, the stronger the acoustic signal and the greater the concentration of eDNA).

We modelled the logarithm of the observed acoustic signal intensity (i.e. NASC), W_i , of anchovies at gridded area i as drawn from a normal distribution with a mean species density, θ_i , and a standard deviation φ :

$$\log_e W_i \sim \text{Normal}(\theta_i, \varphi) \quad (2.1)$$

Likewise, we modelled the logarithm of the observed eDNA density (i.e. copies DNA/L seawater), Y_i , with a normal distribution with a mean concentration, μ_i , and a standard deviation σ_i :

$$\log_e Y_i \sim \text{Normal}(\mu_i, \sigma_i) \quad (2.2)$$

Note that the standard deviation for eDNA was allowed to vary by gridded area because point data is used, while for acoustics it was assumed to be constant in space due to integrated values. Although the number of DNA copies is initially estimated using Poisson statistics within the digital PCR software, the values used in our model are the final concentration estimates (copies/L), calculated after correcting for dilution and extraction volumes, which are continuous and strictly positive values. A constant value (1) was added to all eDNA and NASC data before transforming to the logarithmic scale to obtain valid values for the null observations (i.e. 0 copies/L). Also, all years of data were simultaneously treated because it was assumed that the spatial distribution of anchovies

did not change over time, considering that sampling took place consistently during late early autumn.

The observations from both methods were then related to a shared reality, that is, the underlying fish abundance. Let X_i be the true, but unobserved, biomass (in log scale) of anchovies in grid cell i . The expected means of the lognormal distributions of the observations were linked linearly to the underlying fish biomass (X_i), following a log-log structure that has previously been applied to eDNA and acoustic data modelling (Shelton et al., 2019; Shelton et al. 2022).

Specifically, the mean of the acoustic observation, θ_i , of anchovies at grid cell i was modelled as a linear function,

$$\theta_i = \gamma + \lambda X_i \quad (3.1)$$

and the mean of the eDNA abundance, μ_i , as a linear process,

$$\mu_i = \alpha + \beta X_i \quad (3.2)$$

where α and γ are the intercepts, and β and λ are the coefficients of X_i . Likewise, the standard deviation of the eDNA estimations (σ_i , which is constrained to be a positive value) was an exponential linear function of the fish log biomass (X_i),

$$\sigma_i = \exp(\nu + \delta X_i) \quad (3.3)$$

where ν is the intercept and δ the coefficient of X_i . This formulation captures heteroscedasticity, allowing to the standard deviation of eDNA observation model to vary with biomass.

In this model, we do not describe how biomass is influenced by environmental factors or is spatially correlated to neighbouring cells. Instead, we treat biomass in each grid cell as an independent unknown value. This choice was made to keep the model simple and focus on combining the two types of observations (acoustic and eDNA).

The model was fitted in a Bayesian framework using the prior distributions detailed in Table S2. The sensitivity of the model results to the priors was evaluated by running the model with different prior distributions. The joint model results remained consistent across the different prior distribution runs, indicating that they were not strongly affected by prior parameter values (Figure S3) and that the model's outputs are robust, being driven by the data itself, rather than by initial assumptions.

All the analyses were conducted in Rstudio (version 4.2.2) as an integrated development environment for R. The model was coded and fitted using the package *rstan* (Bürkner 2017) that is based on the Stan programming language. Stan is written in C++ and implements full Bayesian statistical inference using Hamiltonian Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) (Carpenter et al. 2017). The joint model was run with 4 chains, each with 4000 sampling iterations, including a burn-in of half of the total iterations and no thinning was applied. Model convergence was assessed through the R-hat diagnostic (Vehtari et al. 2021) and by visual examination of the resulting correlation plots and chain mixtures (Figure S4). The posterior distribution of the parameters showed that the Markov chains effectively converged (R-hat ≈ 1 ; Table S3), indicating that the model sampling process was stable and consistent. The effective number of independent samples (effective sample size, ESS) ranged between 1200–12 000 (Table S3) with all the ratios of effective sample size to the total number of samples (EES/N) above 0.1 (Figure S5), which ensures reliable estimates. Additionally, autocorrelation plots showed a rapid decay across lags, confirming efficient mixing and effective sampling of the chains (Figures S6–

S7). Finally, the posterior distributions of the biomass in logarithmic scale (X_i) were used to estimate spatial abundance patterns for anchovy in the BoB. The Stan model, developed scripts and corresponding output files are available at GitHub (<https://github.com/cclaver001/IMPACT>).

Evaluation of the contribution of eDNA to the joint model

One of the aims of this work was to determine the contribution of eDNA-derived data and to understand whether adding eDNA data increases or decreases biomass estimates when used together with acoustic data. In order to evaluate the marginal value of eDNA, we fitted a second model in parallel using only the trawl-acoustic section of the model, following the same procedure (hereafter referred to as the acoustic model; Table S4) and compared the change in the estimates between the two independent models, the joint model and the acoustic model, by calculating the difference of the biomass in logarithmic scale ($X_{\text{joint}} - X_{\text{acoustic}}$). The acoustic model converged as well as the joint model (i.e. R-hat values close to 1, large effective sample size and well-mixed chains) (Figure S8; Table S5).

Results

Acoustic and eDNA based anchovy abundance data

A maximum of 22 and a minimum 18 grid cells had acoustic signal for each of the 6 years, with a total of 120 grid cells considered. From them, 80% were positive for anchovy. As expected in light of the known anchovy distribution (Boyra et al. 2013), the acoustic signal (average NASC = 157 m^2NM^{-2}) was higher in the cells adjacent to coast than in those representing more oceanic areas, with the highest acoustic signal ($\approx 1800 \text{ m}^2\text{NM}^{-2}$) detected in the northern coastal French shelf (Fig. 2b).

Regarding the eDNA samples, 93% of the eDNA samples resulted positive for anchovy, with an average value of 470 copies/L and the highest value being 5800 copies/L (Fig. 2c). Most of the samples were collected between the surface and 300 m depth, being the highest DNA concentrations of anchovy DNA found in the first hundred meters of the water column with a decreasing concentration with depth (Figure S9). In some stations, anchovy eDNA was detected in deeper areas than normally expected, which might be related to sinking, given the positive detection in the same area in shallower waters (Harrison et al. 2019). Also, higher DNA concentrations were found in close-to-shore and shallow waters than in oceanic waters, far from shore (Figure S10), matching the known distributions and preferences of anchovies in the area (Boyra et al. 2013).

Performance of the joint model

To assess the model performance, we conducted a posterior predictive check by simulating full datasets of acoustic (W_i) and eDNA (Y_i) observations using the posterior parameter estimates. The simulated values were then compared to the observed data. Both observation types showed strong agreement with their simulated

counterparts, with high Pearson correlation coefficients, indicating that the model reliably captures the structure of the observed data (Figure S11).

Parameters referring to intercepts (alpha, gamma) and slopes (beta, lambda) of the relationship between eDNA and acoustic data with biomass had narrow credible intervals that indicated high precision (Table S3). Fish biomass estimates (X_i) had the widest intervals (i.e. greatest variability), likely due to differences within sites, sampling effort or inherent biological variability. Grid cells with higher biomass estimates had systematically lower standard deviations, indicating greater precision. Analysis of the posterior parameter correlations provided further insight into the model's behaviour and the interdependencies among parameters (Figure S12). A posterior correlation between intercepts alpha and gamma is observed in the model (ESS values ~ 1200). Given that both acoustic and eDNA observations are linked to biomass, this correlation is interpreted as a consequence of their shared dependence on X , and no ecological inference is drawn from it.

A negative correlation between alpha and nu indicates a trade-off in how the eDNA data fits the model: a higher mean eDNA is compensated by a lower estimated variability, and vice versa, to best explain the observed dispersion of eDNA data points, particularly where fish biomass is low. Similarly, the negative correlation between gamma and nu suggests an interdependency between the estimated acoustic signal and the estimated variability in eDNA measurements. This arises because the model jointly estimates parameters for both data sources and the biomass; a stronger acoustic signal might help constrain overall uncertainty, allowing the model to estimate lower variability in the eDNA estimates. Crucially, these correlations align well with the common understanding that higher biomass values might be measured with greater precision, whereas lower values might be more susceptible to variability due to natural stochasticity or noise (Hespanhol et al. 2019). Such posterior parameter interdependencies are a common feature of complex statistical models, especially those involving multiple observation processes linked by shared latent variables, such as the one described in this work.

Biomass estimates of the joint model and differences from the acoustic model

Overall, the joint model linked the information derived from two independent observation methods and provided biomass estimates of anchovies, in units of fish per grid cell (Fig. 3a; Figure S13). In contrast, the acoustic model used only acoustic data to estimate anchovy biomass (Figures S14-S15; Table S5), and the results indicated, consistent with the acoustic signal, that anchovy biomass is mostly located in the continental shelf, concentrated in the areas closest to the shore. In the grid cells where both datasets are available, the joint model estimates the biomass with greater precision. In contrast, in cells without eDNA data, the precision with which the biomass is estimated (based solely on acoustic data) declines accordingly (Table S3; Table S5).

Largely, both acoustic and eDNA data showed similar spatial patterns and, consequently, the two models agreed in about half of the gridded areas (i.e. zero and low values in Fig. 3b). In some gridded areas, instead, eDNA and acoustic data disagreed, and the estimates differed among the models. For instance, the joint model estimated lower anchovy abundance than the acoustic

Figure 3 Distribution and abundance of European anchovy in the BoB for the 6-year period. **(a)** Posterior estimates of anchovy biomass estimates (mean) under the joint model, representing depth-integrated biomass in logarithmic scale. Negative values in logarithmic scale (corresponding to low biomass levels) were replaced by zero. **(b)** Change in posterior estimates of the depth-integrated biomass (mean values of biomass) when applying the joint model, compared to the only acoustic version of the model ($X_{\text{joint}} - X_{\text{acoustic}}$).

model in two cells along the Cantabrian Sea (i.e. negative values in Fig. 3b). This discrepancy stems from the eDNA data, where positive anchovy values were detected in those cells for only one year over the 6-year period, and the joint model diluted the perceived presence of anchovy in those areas. Conversely, according to the joint model, anchovies showed a wider spatial distribution along the continental shelf in both the Spanish and French waters, with a progressive decay in abundance in deeper waters and offshore (Fig. 3a). Compared to the acoustic model, this results in higher values for anchovy in these areas (i.e. positive values in Fig. 3b).

Thus, compared to the acoustic model, the primary contribution of this approach lies in the model's capacity to synthesize information from two independent observation methods: linking

acoustic and eDNA data to a shared latent variable representing true biomass, the joint model leverages their combined use, offering a more comprehensive view than either method alone.

Discussion

Towards an effective integration of eDNA for providing assessment-informative data

Despite the high anticipation surrounding the use of eDNA in fisheries (Gilbey et al. 2021), there have been limited efforts to propose methods for integrating eDNA data into assessment and translat-

ing it into practical information. The independent use of eDNA data to develop a biomass index, as evidenced by Shelton et al. (2022), represents a significant accomplishment that underscores the value and potential of this information source. Essentially, eDNA data adds a unique dimension to our understanding of fish abundance by providing a signal that reflects species presence even when visual or acoustic detections are limited, offering insights into species distribution across broader spatial and temporal scales.

Although oceanographic surveys are currently the best opportunity to collect eDNA broadly in marine areas, eDNA sampling efforts are generally limited during campaigns because they are mostly opportunistic, and datasets of fine scale covered study areas like the one obtained by Shelton et al. (2022) are difficult to obtain. In our study, the opportunistic annual eDNA sampling was limited and did not cover the sampling area evenly. To address this, we merged the time series data, which resulted in a reasonably good overall coverage, although some gaps remained in certain areas. Alternatively, Bayesian joint models are a reliable approach for combining eDNA information with other fisheries data, such as trawls, as demonstrated by Guri et al. (2024). Therefore, we decided to combine eDNA with acoustic-trawl data in a Bayesian joint model, resulting in the first integration these two data sources to produce anchovy biomass estimates in space.

Different data sources offer varying pieces of information which, when combined, can provide more comprehensive and accurate insights. This perspective highlights that integrating multiple lines of evidence can provide a more informed and, thus, more realistic approximation of fish stocks status. For example, catches and acoustic data represent snapshots of a certain moment in a given space, resulting in discrete and heterogeneous records. Instead, eDNA is composed of DNA molecules from fish-derived particles, that create a more uniformly distributed scattered signal in the environment (Shelton et al. 2022). Accordingly, our results showed that high concentrations of anchovy eDNA were more widespread than acoustic signal detections and, accordingly, the joint model estimated higher anchovy abundances in a wider distribution area than the acoustic-only model estimates. This can be explained due to vessel avoidance in challenging sampling areas, such as shallow coastal waters (Draštík and Kubečka 2005, De Robertis and Handegard 2013), which can lead to acoustic derived biomass underestimations. Additionally, when adult anchovies are near rocky bottoms, trawling is not feasible and delayed night trawls are used (Boyra et al. 2016), making it harder to identify acoustic signals. It is also possible that anchovies may have moved away from the sampling location or may be present in the vicinity but not directly in the acoustic transect (i.e. beneath the vessel at the time of sampling). In such cases, eDNA can still be detected due to its persistence in the water and potential local transport (Andruszkiewicz et al. 2019, Silva et al. 2025), thereby providing evidence of recent or nearby fish presence even without acoustic detections. In sum, our results suggest that, when combined with trawl-acoustic data, eDNA data enhances detection sensitivity, potentially addressing false absences of anchovy derived from the acoustic data, thereby making biomass derived from joint estimates more representative and accurate.

In line with this, species-specific assays could also be combined with metabarcoding data to obtain absolute abundances of mul-

tle species. The observed correlations between catch composition and eDNA metabarcoding-derived relative abundances of fish communities (e.g. Thomsen et al. 2016) indicate that eDNA could also provide species-level information and reduce trawling frequency by enabling shallow-water sampling, which can even be performed through continuous water intake without stopping the vessel, saving substantial expedition time. This would support a biomass estimation framework in which acoustics is used for distribution and abundance, eDNA for species composition and abundance, and minimal trawling for calibration and age-size data.

Challenges and strategies for the use of eDNA in stock assessment

Identifying key milestones for integrating eDNA data into fisheries assessment will help focus future efforts. Although improvements like data modelling could facilitate eDNA information integration into stock assessments, some constraints must be considered.

For example, the data for stock assessment derived from the JUVENA survey only include calculations based on juveniles, and current eDNA analyses fail at differentiating among life stages. Thus, understanding the species' biology is critical to properly interpret at eDNA data; for instance, with adults remaining close to the bottom and juveniles forming pelagic shoals near the surface during daytime (Boyra et al. 2016), it is reasonable to assume that the eDNA collected is predominantly from juvenile individuals, as the sampling was conducted during daylight hours in late early autumn. In the future, using epigenetics or environmental RNA, which can provide information about a specific group of individuals of a species, could also help to solve this issue (Stevens and Parsley 2023).

An additional challenge for eDNA-based studies is that eDNA sampling is often opportunistic and sampling effort is significantly smaller than for other methods (e.g. 37 water samples vs 141 trawls in Le Joncour et al. 2024). This may lead to significant variations in dataset sizes, leading to estimates biased towards the most available data when models are applied. Importantly, insufficient spatial overlap of acoustic and eDNA data diminished the precision and, thus, the ecological interpretability of joint biomass estimates. This is likely to happen in scientific surveys that are focused on a specific methodology, such as JUVENA, where the acoustic effort is considerably bigger than the eDNA sampling effort and underscores the importance of coordinated and spatially representative sampling strategies in future surveys. Indeed, incorporating a new sampling methodology into a well-established survey can be challenging, especially when the nature of the new method is different. For instance, in our case, the acoustic data is collected continuously across transects whereas eDNA is sampled in point-stations, so that the vessel must interrupt the acoustic sampling to deploy the Niskin bottles. In recent years, automatic eDNA samplers have been developed (George et al. 2024) and can represent a promising sampling strategy to combine eDNA and acoustic sampling onboard. However, passive eDNA sampling would only be feasible to collect water from the surface through continuous water intake systems of the vessels, which might not be as representative as vertical profile sampling. Given that most pelagic species make nocturnal vertical migrations to the surface, this could be overcome by carrying out the continuous sampling during the night, as in Shelton et al. 2022.

On the other hand, one of the major limitations of this work is the integration of data from a time series, as annual estimates are needed for evaluation purposes if the results are to be used directly in stock assessment. Due to limited spatial coverage of eDNA sampling in individual years, we aggregated data across the six-year period to maximize spatial coverage and overlap between eDNA and acoustic data. While this approach allowed us to explore the feasibility of integrating both data types in a joint framework, it does not capture interannual variability in fish abundance, which is critical for stock monitoring and management. As such, this is a pilot study that lays the foundation for future consistent annual sampling that will allow repeating these analyses for each year to come. Ideally, the eDNA effort should be increased (Cote et al. 2023) and a robust sampling design that could be repeated and be consistent along time should be established, aiming for spatially and temporally representative coverage. In the case of JUVENA, since 2024, eDNA sampling has started to match hydrological stations, which are fixed and provide a more homogeneous spatial coverage that is stable across the years. This approach improves the representativeness and consistency of the data and will allow to provide yearly estimates in the future.

One way for avoiding weakening the eDNA information due to the lower sample size is to weight data differently when using the models. In this work, we have reduced the acoustic data to cells and maximised the eDNA information by using all water samples separately, without combining them. Because the eDNA sampling locations and effort was variable across the 6-year period, the size of the grids used in this study was determined to obtain at least one eDNA value per most of the gridded areas, ensuring a consistent coverage across the study region. However, a bigger sampling effort with a larger spatial coverage would allow to draw smaller cells and could be an interesting advancement in future surveys to obtain more detailed maps.

While our model usefully combines acoustic and eDNA data, it does not yet include a description of how fish biomass varies across space and time or responds to environmental conditions. This was a deliberate simplification to focus on integrating the two observation methods. Although anchovy biomass is likely influenced by factors such as depth, temperature and vertical transport, these sources of bias are assumed to be minor at the spatial resolution of our grid cells, and therefore the ecology of eDNA is not explicitly considered. Including these aspects in future models could help improve the accuracy and ecological relevance of biomass estimates. In sum, identifying these improvements provides a roadmap for future developments based on work such as that described in this manuscript.

Conclusion

Here, we have successfully combined anchovy acoustic-trawl and eDNA based abundance data and show that the resulted joint distribution and abundance patterns obtained are consistent with the current knowledge of anchovy in the BoB. The versatility of Bayesian models allows the joint model proposed here to be used with different input data (other than eDNA and acoustic trawl) and species, which increases its potential use in other case studies. Also, this work exemplifies how eDNA data can

be used as quality control of acoustic indices, detecting potential catchability problems, and thus helping to improve the robustness and precision of the acoustic estimates. This integrated approach not only utilizes the complementary nature of the data but also provides valuable insights into the relationship between acoustic signals, eDNA concentrations, and biomass. This study highlights the need for integrated, well-designed sampling strategies that couple eDNA and acoustics, advancing methodological development and setting a benchmark for future research.

Data availability

The data underlying this article are available in GitHub and can be accessed at <https://github.com/cclaver001/IMPACT>.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to the crew of R/V Angeles Alvaríño and Emma Bardán, specially to Carlota Pérez, Naiara Serrano and Deniz Kukul, for their support during sample collection, and to Aitor Lekanda and Iosu Paradinas, for helping with the acoustic data interpretation and for providing feedback on the model, respectively. The authors would like to thank “The eDNA Collaborative” team, and particularly Andrew Olaf Shelton, for providing the foundations on which current work lies, as well as relevant input throughout the development of the project. We also want to thank the three reviewers for their constructive feedback, which contributed to improve the manuscript.

Author contributions

Beatriz Sobradillo (Investigation [equal], Resources [equal], Writing—review & editing [equal]), Oriol Canals (Investigation [equal], Writing—review & editing [equal]), Iñaki Mendibil (Investigation [equal], Writing—review & editing [equal]), Guillermo Boyra (Funding acquisition [equal], Investigation [equal], Resources [equal], Writing—review & editing [equal]), Leire Ibaibarriaga (Software [equal], Validation [equal], Writing—review & editing [equal]), Ryan P Kelly (Conceptualization [equal], Formal Analysis [equal], Investigation [equal], Methodology [equal], Software [equal], Writing—original draft [equal], Writing—review & editing [equal]), Naiara Rodríguez-Ezpeleta (Funding acquisition [equal], Resources [equal], Writing - original draft [equal], Writing—review & editing [equal]).

Supplementary material

Supplementary data is available at *ICES Journal of Marine Science* online.

Conflicts of interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding

The JUVENA survey is co-funded by the Department of Economic Development, Sustainability and the Environment, by the Vice-Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food Policy of the Directorate of Fisheries and Aquaculture of the Basque Government, as well as by the Spanish Institute of Oceanography of the Ministry of Science and Innovation and by the General Secretariat of Fisheries of the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA) of the Spanish Government. This work has been funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (project OBAMA-NEXT with grant agreement No. 101081642, project BIOcean5D with grant agreement No. 101059915) and the Department of Education (Basque Government) through a predoctoral grant to Cristina Claver.

References

- Albaina A, Irigoien X, Aldalur U *et al.* A real-time PCR assay to estimate invertebrate and fish predation on anchovy eggs in the Bay of Biscay. *Prog Oceanogr* 2015;**131**:82–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2014.12.002>
- Andruszkiewicz EA, Koseff JR, Fringer OB *et al.* Modeling environmental DNA transport in the coastal ocean using lagrangian particle tracking. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 2019;**6**:477. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00477>
- Barange M, Bernal M, Cergole MC *et al.* Current trends in the assessment and management of stocks. In: Checkley D, Alheit J, Oozeki Y, *et al.* (eds.), *Climate Change and Small Pelagic Fish*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press 2009 191–255
- Borja A, Amouroux D, Anschutz P *et al.* The bay of biscay. In: *World Seas: an Environmental Evaluation*. London: Elsevier, 2019, 113–52.
- Boyra G, Cotano U, Martinez U *et al.* JUVENA series review of the spatial distribution of anchovy juveniles in the Bay of Biscay. In: *XI International Symposium on Oceanography of the Bay of Biscay, San Sebastián (Spain)* 2008
- Boyra G, Martínez U, Cotano U *et al.* Acoustic surveys for juvenile anchovy in the Bay of Biscay: abundance estimate as an indicator of the next year's recruitment and spatial distribution patterns. *ICES J Mar Sci* 2013;**70**:1354–68. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fst096>
- Boyra G, Peña M, Cotano U *et al.* Spatial dynamics of juvenile anchovy in the Bay of Biscay. *Fisheries Oceanography* 2016;**25**:529–43. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fog.12170>
- Boyra G, Sobradillo B, Rico I *et al.* Acoustic surveying of anchovy juveniles in the Bay of Biscay: juvena 2023 survey report. In: *Technical Report, Working Document to ICES WGACEGG Meeting*. Lisboa, Portugal. 2023.
- Bürkner P-C. brms: an R package for bayesian multilevel models using Stan. *J Stat Softw* 2017;**80**:1–28.
- Carpenter B, Gelman A, Hoffman MD *et al.* Stan: a probabilistic programming language. *J Stat Softw* 2017;**76**:1–32. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v076.i01>
- Checkley DM, Asch RG, Rykaczewski RR. Climate, anchovy, and sardine. *Annual Review of Marine Science* 2017;**9**:469–93. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-122414-033819>
- Chevrais M, Bourret A, Côté G *et al.* Improving an endangered marine species distribution using reliable and localized environmental DNA detections combined with trawl captures. *Sci Rep* 2025;**15**:1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-95358-3>
- Cote D, McClenaghan B, Desforges J *et al.* Comparing eDNA metabarcoding and conventional pelagic netting to inform biodiversity monitoring in deep ocean environments. *ICES J Mar Sci* 2023;**80**:2545–62. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsad169>
- De Robertis A, Handegard NO. Fish avoidance of research vessels and the efficacy of noise-reduced vessels: a review. *ICES J Mar Sci* 2013;**70**:34–45. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fss155>
- Demer DA, Berger L, Bernasconi M *et al.* Calibration of acoustic instruments. ICES Cooperative Research Report No. 326. 2015;133. <https://doi.org/10.17895/ices.pub.5494>
- Doi H, Uchii K, Takahara T *et al.* Use of droplet digital PCR for estimation of fish abundance and biomass in environmental DNA surveys. *PLoS One* 2015;**10**:e0122763. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0122763>
- Doray M, Boyra G, van der Kooij J. ICES survey protocols—Manual for acoustic surveys coordinated under ICES working group on acoustic and egg surveys for small pelagic fish (WGACEGG). *ICES techniques in marine environmental sciences* 2021;**64**:1–100.
- Draštík V, Kubečka J. Fish avoidance of acoustic survey boat in shallow waters. *Fish Res* 2005;**72**:219–28.
- Eichmiller JJ, Miller LM, Sorensen PW. Optimizing techniques to capture and extract environmental DNA for detection and quantification of fish. *Mol Ecol Resour* 2016;**16**:56–68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.12421>
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). In: *The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture*. Rome: Blue Transformation in Action, 2024.
- Fleischer G, Cooke KD, Ressler PH *et al.* The 2003 integrated acoustic and trawl survey of Pacific hake, *Merluccius productus*, in US and Canadian waters off the Pacific coast. *U.S. Department of Commerce, NOAA Technical Memorandum* 2005;**NMFS-NWFSC-65**: 1–45.
- Fraija-Fernández N, Bouquieaux MC, Rey A *et al.* Marine water environmental DNA metabarcoding provides a comprehensive fish diversity assessment and reveals spatial patterns in a large oceanic area. *Ecology and Evolution* 2020;**10**:7560–84. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.6482>
- Fréon P, Cury P, Shannon L *et al.* Sustainable exploitation of small pelagic fish stocks challenged by environmental and ecosystem changes: a review. *Bull Mar Sci* 2005;**76**:385–462.
- George SD, Sepulveda AJ, Hutchins PR *et al.* Field trials of an autonomous eDNA sampler in lotic waters. *Environ Sci Technol* 2024;**58**:20942–53. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.4c04970>
- Gilbey J, Carvalho G, Castilho R *et al.* Life in a drop: sampling environmental DNA for marine fishery management and ecosystem monitoring. *Mar Policy* 2021;**124**:104331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.104331>
- Guri G, Shelton AO, Kelly RP *et al.* Predicting trawl catches using environmental DNA. *ICES J Mar Sci* 2024;fsae097.
- Harrison JB, Sunday JM, Rogers SM. Predicting the fate of eDNA in the environment and implications for studying biodiversity. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B* 2019;**286**:20191409. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2019.1409>

- Hespanhol L, Vallio CS, Costa LM *et al.* Understanding and interpreting confidence and credible intervals around effect estimates. *Brazilian journal of physical therapy* 2019;**23**:290–301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjpt.2018.12.006>
- ICES. Bay of Biscay and the Iberian Coast ecoregion—Fisheries overview. Report of the ICES Advisory Committee, 2022
- Iglesias B, Louzao M, Preciado I *et al.* Identifying bottlenecks to energy circulation in the Bay of Biscay pelagic food web: key species under the spotlight: B. Iglesias and others. *Ecosystems* 2025;**28**:43. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-025-00990-9>
- Karlsson E, Ogonowski M, Sundblad G *et al.* Strong positive relationships between eDNA concentrations and biomass in juvenile and adult pike (*Esox lucius*) under controlled conditions: implications for monitoring. *Environmental DNA* 2022;**4**:881–93. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.298>
- Klymus KE, Richter CA, Chapman DC *et al.* Quantification of eDNA shedding rates from invasive bighead carp *Hypophthalmichthys nobilis* and silver carp *Hypophthalmichthys molitrix*. *Biol Conserv* 2015;**183**:77–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2014.11.020>
- Knudsen SW, Ebert RB, Hesselsøe M *et al.* Species-specific detection and quantification of environmental DNA from marine fishes in the Baltic Sea. *J Exp Mar Biol Ecol* 2019;**510**:31–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2018.09.004>
- Lacoursière-Roussel A, Côté G, Leclerc V *et al.* Quantifying relative fish abundance with eDNA: a promising tool for fisheries management. *J Appl Ecol* 2016;**53**:1148–57. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12598>
- Le Joncour A, Mouchet M, Boussarie G *et al.* Is it worthy to use environmental DNA instead of scientific trawling or video survey to monitor taxa in soft-bottom habitats? *Mar Environ Res* 2024;**200**:106667. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2024.106667>
- Maes SM, Desmet S, Brys R *et al.* Detection and quantification of two commercial flatfishes (*Solea solea* and *Pleuronectes platessa*) in the North Sea using environmental DNA. *Environmental DNA* 2024;**6**:e426. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.426>
- Maiello G, Talarico L, Carpentieri P *et al.* Little samplers, big fleet: eDNA metabarcoding from commercial trawlers enhances ocean monitoring. *Fish Res* 2022;**249**:106259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2022.106259>
- Saba GK, Burd AB, Dunne JP *et al.* Toward a better understanding of fish-based contribution to ocean carbon flux. *Limnol Oceanogr* 2021;**66**:1639–64. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lno.11709>
- Salter I, Joensen M, Kristiansen R *et al.* Environmental DNA concentrations are correlated with regional biomass of Atlantic cod in oceanic waters. *Commun Biol* 2019;**2**:461. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-019-0696-8>
- Sánchez S, Ibaibarriaga L, Uriarte A *et al.* Challenges of management strategy evaluation for small pelagic fish: the Bay of Biscay anchovy case study. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 2019;**617**:245–63. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps12602>
- Shaffer MR, Andruszkiewicz Allan E, Van Cise AM *et al.* Observation bias in metabarcoding. *Mol Ecol Resour* 2025;**25**:e14119 <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.14119>
- Shelton AO, Kelly RP, O'Donnell JL, *et al.* Environmental DNA provides quantitative estimates of a threatened salmon species. *Biological Conservation* 2019;**237**:383–391.
- Shelton AO, Gold ZJ, Jensen AJ *et al.* Toward quantitative metabarcoding. *Ecology* 2023;**104**:e3906. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecy.3906>
- Shelton AO, Ramón-Laca A, Wells A *et al.* Environmental DNA provides quantitative estimates of Pacific hake abundance and distribution in the open ocean. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B* 2022;**289**:20212613. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2021.2613>
- Silva TA, Beraud C, Lamb PD *et al.* Modelling the spatial bound of an eDNA signal in the marine environment—the effect of local conditions. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 2025;**12**:1613001. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2025.1613001>
- Simmonds J, MacLennan DN. *Fisheries Acoustics: Theory and Practice*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2008.
- Spens J, Evans AR, Halfmaerten D *et al.* Comparison of capture and storage methods for aqueous microbial eDNA using an optimized extraction protocol: advantage of enclosed filter. *Methods Ecol Evol* 2017;**8**:635–45. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12683>
- Stenevik EK, Vølstad JH, Høines Å *et al.* Precision in estimates of density and biomass of Norwegian spring-spawning herring based on acoustic surveys. *Mar Biol Res* 2015;**11**:449–61. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17451000.2014.995672>
- Stevens JD, Parsley MB. Environmental RNA applications and their associated gene targets for management and conservation. *Environmental DNA* 2023;**5**:227–39. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.386>
- Stoeckle MY, Adolf J, Charlop-Powers Z *et al.* Trawl and eDNA assessment of marine fish diversity, seasonality, and relative abundance in coastal New Jersey, USA. *ICES J Mar Sci* 2021;**78**:293–304. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsaa225>
- Takahara T, Minamoto T, Yamanaka H *et al.* Estimation of fish biomass using environmental DNA. *PLoS One* 2012;**7**:e35868. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0035868>
- Thomsen PF, Møller PR, Sigsgaard EE *et al.* Environmental DNA from seawater samples correlate with trawl catches of subarctic, deepwater fishes. *PLoS One* 2016;**11**:e0165252. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0165252>
- Uriarte A, Ibaibarriaga L, Sánchez-Maróño S *et al.* Lessons learnt on the management of short-lived fish from the Bay of Biscay anchovy case study: satisfying fishery needs and sustainability under recruitment uncertainty. *Mar Policy* 2023;**150**:105512. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2023.105512>
- Vehtari A, Gelman A, Simpson D *et al.* Rank-normalization, folding, and localization: an improved \hat{R} for assessing convergence of MCMC (with discussion). *Bayesian analysis* 2021;**16**:667–718. <https://doi.org/10.1214/20-BA1221>
- Veron P, Rozanski R, Marques V *et al.* Environmental DNA complements scientific trawling in surveys of marine fish biodiversity. *ICES J Mar Sci* 2023;**80**:2150–65. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsad139>
- Wood SA, Pochon X, Laroche O *et al.* A comparison of droplet digital polymerase chain reaction (PCR), quantitative PCR and metabarcoding for species-specific detection in environmental DNA. *Mol Ecol Resour* 2019;**19**:1407–19. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.13055>

Zhang J, Chen X, Zhou Q *et al.* Species identification and biomass assessment of *gnathanodon speciosus* based on environmental DNA technology. *Ecol Indic* 2024;**160**:111821. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.111821>

Zhou S, Fan C, Xia H *et al.* Combined use of eDNA metabarcoding and bottom trawling for the assessment of fish biodiversity in the Zhoushan Sea. *Frontiers in marine science* 2022;**8**:809703. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.809703>

Handling editor: Richard O'Driscoll